

The Impact of COVID-19 on E-Commerce Employment in the U.S.

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic's onset correlated with a shift in customer preference toward e-commerce platforms. This paper examines e-commerce employment data from the Federal Reserve Economic Data of the St. Louis Branch of Federal Reserve (FRED) in the nation and four states: California, Florida, Indiana, and Wisconsin. Only the years 2008-22 are considered for this study. It analyzes the trends in employment growth before and after the pandemic to conclude whether or not the pandemic permanently changed the e-commerce industry. These four states—representing two distinctive regions of the country- used the Linear Regression Model and Chow Test to test if a structural change in the trends of e-commerce employment occurred in the onset of the pandemic in the U.S. and if such changes were permanent. The paper concludes that despite an initial structural break point occurring during the pandemic, post-pandemic e-commerce employment growth remained similar to that of the pre-pandemic era.

***Keywords:** Structural Change, COVID-19, E-commerce, Employment*

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic led to disruptions in the retail industry. E-commerce, which already saw pre-pandemic growth in sales and transactions, saw an increase in the size of the total retail market share within the retail market from 11.9% in the first quarter of 2020 to 16% in the second quarter of 2024 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024). This is because customers have turned to a method (online) of shopping that can still be done on a large scale during lockdowns (Briedis, 2020).

The United States lockdown spanned a longer time than other developed nations like Italy or China and led to a mass exodus in major cities as numerous people lost

their jobs (Visé, 2023). Furthermore, the US government became more financially strained due to the pandemic, as the government desperately sent out stimulus checks to Americans—especially those who lost their paychecks (Pramuk, 2020).

The retail market especially took a downfall. Traditional retail, which already had financial burdens before the pandemic, experienced the biggest share of the burden. Corporations like Sears and Lord and Taylor laid off numerous employees and declared bankruptcy (McDowell, 2020).

Given the attention to e-commerce during the pandemic, the paper examines the question: To what extent did the COVID-19 pandemic permanently change the trend of e-commerce employment in the US and four states (California, Florida, Indiana, and Wisconsin)?

The reason for these states being chosen for analysis is due to the regional differences between them. California and Florida are Sunbelt states, while Indiana and Wisconsin are Rust Belt states (Wallenfeldt, 2024; T. Editors of Encyclopedia).

Both Florida and California are large, diverse states. California is on the West Coast and has a cosmopolitan population—it is a minority-majority state (United States Census Bureau, 2024). Florida has a large Hispanic population and shares a mix of rural, urban, and suburban populations (United States Census Bureau, 2018). Florida and California have experienced population growth in the past two decades (United States Census Bureau, 2024; United States Census Bureau, 2018). The two states had stark contrasts in their responses to the pandemic's outbreak, with California taking strict measures and Florida taking a more lenient approach (Shannon, 2021; Stanage, 2021). They represent two distinct case studies for the growing Sunbelt region.

Wisconsin and Indiana, unlike California and Florida, are mid-sized states in terms of population (US Census Bureau, 2024). In this region, a steady net migration out of the region due to the decline of manufacturing jobs in the nation (Wallenfeldt, 2024). Politically, Indiana and Wisconsin are different from each other. Wisconsin is a swing state. Indiana, on the other hand, has traditionally been a Republican stronghold (Cook Political Report, 2024). Thus, Indiana and Wisconsin give different contexts to a region different from the southern Sunbelt.

The paper examines employment growth in e-commerce through the data provided by the Federal Reserve Economic Data (FRED) posted on the St Louis Federal Reserve Branch. These data sets measure raw e-commerce employment in four states and the United States. The paper splits its analysis of trends into two areas: pre-pandemic trends and post-pandemic trends. Since COVID-19 caused a drastic downturn in e-commerce employment in the first quarter of 2020, the paper uses a time series structural break analysis algorithm to prove that March 2020 is the structural break point.

Based on the analyzed results, the paper finds that there is a structural breakpoint at the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, in which in all states, the e-commerce population increased as a result. However, such rapid growth was not sustained in the post-pandemic era.

1.1 Literature Review

The paper's methodology is based on a few methods. Alawan et al. assessed the pandemic's impacts of the lockdowns on brick-and-mortar retail and the e-commerce industry. The researchers analyzed the economies of four Middle Eastern countries- United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, and Kuwait during the pandemic. The researchers used ranking impacts (Gray Analytical Hierarchy Process) to each economy and responses (Gray Relational Analysis) to the changes made. This research was applied to analyzing supply chains and potential disruptions, providing context to analyzing potential disruptions in e-commerce. The researchers found that the pandemic drove shoppers towards e-commerce, but the pandemic also harmed e-commerce efficiency.

Cyzurlo (2021) analyzed the relationship between employment and e-commerce during the pandemic. According to the study, an employee's level of engagement with e-commerce may have impacted their ability to stay employed during the pandemic. This is especially true for businesses that do not have a large online presence and require in-person exchanges or transactions. Surveying metro areas in the US with data from the Census Bureau, Cyzurlo argues that employees with higher interactions with e-commerce have a greater likelihood of job retention during the

pandemic, which aligns with how Florida and California seemed to retain the increased levels of e-commerce employment compared to Wisconsin and Indiana.

Although there was a temporary boost in e-commerce sales in the US, it did not change e-commerce sales growth. Mendez-Carbajo (2022) uses similar approaches to this paper to answer the question. Carbajo notes how the line representing e-commerce as a percentage of total retail sales grows parallel to the raw retail sales value and spikes during the pandemic. However, this trend stops in the post-pandemic world as the percentage of e-commerce in relation to total sales has gone down—a very similar finding to this paper on employment.

Check et al. (2021) assessed the evidence for structural breakpoints in autoregressive models of U.S. macroeconomic time series. He develops a Bayesian model averaging approach to solve the source uncertainty problem, such as lag selection, number of structural breaks, and specific number of parameters that break. Check's paper focuses on analyzing multiple structural breaks. His paper cautions against relying on one model for analyzing structural changes in trends, pointing it may not always be accurate. However, unlike Check's paper, the purpose of this paper is to verify the existence of a breakpoint in e-commerce employment during the onset of the pandemic. Thus, a linear regression model and Chow test are better suited to answer if a structural break did occur.

Luitel et al. (2015) applied the Chow Test to assess whether the switch from reporting GDP through the Standard Industrial Classification Model to the North American Industrial Classification System caused a structural break in the recorded GDP data. This provides a good example of how a disruption to normal processes can have its impact evaluated through a Chow test, which the paper will use with regard to the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on e-commerce employment.

Many papers examine e-commerce sales and revenue before and after the pandemic, but a gap exists in the current literature review when it comes to analyzing e-commerce employment. Given the rise of e-commerce within the retail industry, e-commerce may provide a route for retail to permanently adapt to a digital environment. Analyzing employment in the industry will evaluate the industry in a different light and offer insights into the industry's robustness. The objective of this

paper is to find if the pandemic's onset coincided with a structural change in the trend of e-commerce and whether that trend has lasted or changed in the post-pandemic era.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Aim of Study

The study aims to fill the gap in the existing literature: Did the COVID-19 pandemic correlate with a permanent increase in employment in the e-commerce industry? The goal is to provide a different lens in measuring the robustness of an industry that has largely been analyzed through sales and profits rather than the number of people who rely on it directly for income.

2.2 Research Design

The paper adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data and macroeconomic analysis. The quantitative analysis includes e-commerce employment statistics from the FRED of St. Louis. The qualitative component involves case studies of the four states' (California, Florida, Indiana, and Wisconsin) e-commerce employment trends before and after the pandemic and time series structural break analysis. The paper uses both the Chow test and the T-test. In both tests, the independent variable is time, and the dependent variable is employees per thousand of people.

2.3 Hypothesis

The study uses two sets of alternative and null hypotheses. The first set is for the Chow Test:

- **Null:** There is no structural change in the trend of e-commerce employment on March 1st, 2020
- **Alternative:** otherwise

The second set is for the t-test:

- **Null:** There is no change in the trend of e-commerce employment between the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic eras
- **Alternative:** otherwise

2.4 Ethical Considerations

The paper follows ethical guidelines of research, including using publicly accessible data sets from the Federal Reserve. No data was extracted from uninformed respondents or unofficial records.

2.5 Data Collection and Procedure

The paper uses four datasets from the FRED for employment in e-commerce for California, Florida, Indiana, and Wisconsin from 2008 to 2022. To keep the window of analysis consistent, the paper only uses data from the start of 2008—given that Indiana’s e-commerce employment data is from January 2008 to December 2022. All datasets collect the monthly e-commerce employment in the unit of thousands of persons.

The paper also uses the 2008-2023 US annual e-commerce employment dataset and the US monthly unemployment rate dataset from the FRED. All variables (employment levels in the e-commerce industry and the unemployment rate) in the datasets provided by the Federal Reserve are seasonally adjusted. These datasets are used as a baseline for the COVID-19 impact analysis.

The data sets included from the FRED are listed below.

- All Employees: Retail Trade: Electronic Shopping and Mail-Order Houses in: California, Florida, Indiana, Wisconsin, United States
- Unemployment Rate in California, Florida, Indiana, Wisconsin

Figure 1: US Monthly National Unemployment Rate (1990-2024)

The graph above depicts the US national unemployment rate from 1990 to 2024. There is a notable spike in unemployment in 2020 that appears much more sudden and immediate than the other spikes, such as the ones during 2007-09 and the 2001 recession. Thus, the initial evidence suggests that there is a significant structural break point in 2020.

All employment data was then adjusted to make sure the unemployment rate would not impact the given data. This was done via the formula:

$$\text{Adjusted Employment} = \frac{\text{Raw Employment}}{1 - \text{Unemployment Rate}}$$

Where raw employment is the number of employees working at a given month and year according to the FRED data and the unemployment rate is the percentage of people among the population who are not employed at a given time and state according to the FRED data.

The first step is to analyze the extent of the pandemic’s initial impact on the level of e-commerce employment. In order to do so, each of the time series datasets is split into two sections: the pre-pandemic section and the post-pandemic section. A cut-off point on March 1, 2020, was selected to create a pre-pandemic dataset and a post-pandemic dataset. This was because March was the month when lockdowns were implemented nationally. Then, the Chow test is applied to demonstrate the independent variable (the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic) to identify a structural break point in each of the models. The paper will also compare and contrast each time series’s parameters.

According to the Chow Test, if a structural change does not exist between the primary and secondary sets, a regression can be run over the whole dataset, and it will not result in biased estimators (Bobbitt, 2021).

The residual sum of squares (to find the variance, or error in our regression models) is calculated for the whole samples with Equation (1). Equation 1 is the linear regression equation for the adjusted employee population. Equation 2 is the formula applied to the pre-pandemic dataset (Sample A). Equation 3 is the formula applied to the post-pandemic dataset (Sample B). Then the residual sum of squares for the full dataset ample P), Sample A, and Sample B are computed using equation (4).

$$Y_{i_p} = \beta_{1_p} + \beta_{2_p} x_{i_p} + \varepsilon_i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n) \quad (1)$$

$$Y_{i_A} = \beta_{1_A} + \beta_{2_A} x_{i_A} + \varepsilon_i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, m) \quad (2)$$

$$Y_{i_B} = \beta_{1_B} + \beta_{2_B} x_{i_B} + \varepsilon_i \quad (i = m + 1, m + 2, \dots, n) \quad (3)$$

$$RSS = \sum_{i=1}^t (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

Where:

- P stands for the pooled sample, A stands for the pre-pandemic sample, and B stands for the post-pandemic sample
- n is the total size of data points in the entire sample
- m is the total size of data points in the pre-March 1st, 2020 sample
- n-m is the total size of data points in the post-March 1st, 2020 sample
- Y_i is the dependent variable (adjusted employee population in e-commerce)
- x_i is the independent variable (time)
- β_1 is the intercept
- β_2 is the slope
- $\varepsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ identically and independently distributed residuals
 $i = 1, \dots, n$.

Below are the null and alternative hypotheses:

- Null Hypothesis H_0 : There is no structural break in the dataset on March 1, 2020
- Alternative Hypothesis H_1 : There is a structural break in the dataset on March 1, 2020

The Chow test is an F-test that will display whether or not a structural break point coincided with the onset of the pandemic. The structural break will represent a clear change in the trend of the employee population. The test follows the F-statistic:

$$F = \frac{(RSS_P - RSS_A - RSS_B) / k}{(RSS_A + RSS_B) / (n - 2k)}$$

Where,

- RSS_P is the residual sum of squares for the entire dataset
- RSS_A is the residual sum of squares for sample A (pre-March 1st, 2020 dataset)
- RSS_B is the residual sum of squares for sample B (post-March 1st, 2020 dataset)
- RSS_P, RSS_A, RSS_B are computed using equation (4) by replacing Y_i with Y_{i_P}, Y_{i_A} , and Y_{i_B}, \hat{Y}_i with the predicted corresponding values

The variable k refers to the number of variables in the regression model for the null hypothesis (H_0). The F statistic involves the F-distribution with k and $n - 2k$ as degrees of freedom. The F-critical value is calculated given $k = 2, n = 180$; so the F-critical value is 3.047. If the F-statistic is greater than the F-critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected, if otherwise, the null hypothesis remains not rejected. A rejection of the null hypothesis indicates that the onset of the pandemic coincided with a change in the trend of e-commerce employment.

To answer the second component of the question—the extent to which the pandemic permanently impacted the e-commerce employee population—the t-test was applied to see if there was any significant difference in trend lines between the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic eras. Thus, the Chow test analyzes if there was a change in the trend of the e-commerce employee population at the onset of the pandemic, and the t-test assesses if there is a change in the trends between the pre- and post-pandemic periods.

While the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic periods are defined as before February 2020 and after February 2021, respectively, the COVID-19 recession in the research paper is defined as the initial shockwave by the Federal Reserve—spanning from March 2020 to March 2021 (FRED, 2024). The data from the dates in between these periods was not used due to the temporary initial shock of the pandemic. This is because quarantines and

uncontrolled surges created outliers when assessing trends in e-commerce employment growth.

Using the t-test, the whole data set of each state (California, Florida, Indiana, and Wisconsin) was first split into three data sets. Since there are structural change breaks during COVID-19 from the previous structural analysis session, only before and after COVID-19 datasets are used for trend analysis.

- Pre-pandemic (Before February 1st, 2020)
 - n_{pre} is the number of data points in the pre-pandemic dataset (126 data points)
- during pandemic (March 1st, 2020 to January 1st, 2021)
- post-pandemic (February 1st, 2021 to December 1st, 2022)
 - n_{post} is the number of data points in the post-pandemic dataset (23 data points)

Then, a linear fit regression model was applied to both the pre- and post-pandemic data sets. The data taken during the pandemic was discarded due to the initial drop in e-commerce employment not providing accurate data for the pandemic’s long-term impacts on e-commerce. For each data set, the two following equations and rules were applied:

$$Y_{i_{pre}} = \beta_{1_{pre}} + \beta_{2_{pre}} x_{i_{pre}} + \varepsilon_i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n_{pre}) \quad (5)$$

$$Y_{i_{post}} = \beta_{1_{post}} + \beta_{2_{post}} x_{i_{post}} + \varepsilon_i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n_{post}) \quad (6)$$

Where, $\varepsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ identically and independently distributed residuals for all i

In the linear regression, the following formula was used to calculate the t-statistic for comparing the slopes of two datasets:

$$t = \frac{\hat{\beta}_{2_{post}} - \hat{\beta}_{2_{pre}}}{\sqrt{SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{pre}}}^2 + SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{post}}}^2}} \quad (7)$$

Where, $SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{pre}}}$ and $SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{post}}}$ are the standard errors of the slopes

To compute the critical t-value for a given degree of freedom and significance level. The significance level was 0.05, and the confidence level was 95%. The standard errors are computed taking into account the different sample sizes n_{pre} and n_{post} . Equation 8 was used to determine the degrees of freedom:

$$df = \frac{\left(\frac{SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{pre}}}^2 + SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{post}}}^2}{\frac{SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{pre}}}^4}{n_{pre}-2} + \frac{SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{post}}}^4}{n_{post}-2}} \right)^2}{\frac{SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{pre}}}^4}{n_{pre}-2} + \frac{SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{post}}}^4}{n_{post}-2}} \quad (8)$$

Where n_{pre} and n_{post} are the sample sizes of the two datasets (pre-pandemic and post-pandemic).

Using the t-distribution table, the calculated t-statistic (written as $|t|$) was compared to the critical t-value (threshold for whether or not to reject the null hypothesis) for the above df and significance level:

- **Null Hypothesis:** There is no permanent impact from the COVID-19 pandemic on the current rate of change of the e-commerce employment-population
- **Alternative Hypothesis:** There is a permanent impact from the COVID-19 pandemic on the current rate of change of the e-commerce employment-population

If $|t|$ is greater than the critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the slopes are significantly different. If not, the null hypothesis remains, and no significant difference exists between the pre- and post-pandemic slopes.

3. RESULTS

The data below lists all the observations for each time series set. All the data below was seasonally adjusted.

From initial observations, the e-commerce employment-population overall has grown. California and Florida especially have seen steady growth rates—with California’s pre-pandemic growth being the quickest. It comes as no surprise that California and Florida’s employment populations are larger than that of Indiana and Wisconsin, given that the former two states are the largest and third largest states by population, respectively.

A simple linear regression model—Ordinal Least squares, in which the independent variable is the raw data- will be applied to the state e-commerce employment time series data in order to capture the linear trends for each time series. The graph below depicts the employment populations for each state along with the split dates.

Figure 2: The Adjusted Employee Population for all Four States. The dashed line identifies the structural break on March 1, 2020.

Table 2 Chow Test: F-Statistic and F Critical Value Calculations

Chow Test Results	California	Florida	Indiana	Wisconsin
RSS_P	923.7107	380.4414	226.0510	44.7739
RSS_A	689.4775	53.8889	114.5827	33.5925
RSS_B	39.7723	48.4769	19.5170	6.2088

Chow Test Results	California	Florida	Indiana	Wisconsin
n	180	180	180	180
k	2	2	2	2
F-Statistic	23.4659	239.0509	60.3409	10.9942
F-Critical Value	3.047	3.047	3.047	3.047
Significance Level	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
H_0 : no break change	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected

The table above for the Chow test lists the values for the RSS_P , RSS_A , RSS_B , n , k , F -statistic, F -Critical Value, and Significance level variables (the components of the OLS results). It indicates as well whether the Null Hypothesis (H_0) was rejected or not. According to the Chow test results, the F-statistic value is greater than the F-critical value for all four states, which means that for every state, the null hypothesis was rejected. It indicates that the F-Statistic value is greater than the F critical value for all four states: California, Florida, Indiana, and Wisconsin. According to the Chow test, the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore, there is a structural break point in each state e-commerce employment time series pooled sample. This is, therefore, in line with the initial evidence provided by the graph of the US unemployment rate.

The paper also examined whether an imbalance in the number of data points before and after COVID-19 played a role in the initial Chow test results. The second Chow test was performed, examining the same data point (March 2020) and narrowing the pre-pandemic data setting it from January 2017 to February 2020. For three of the four states, the results remained unchanged, meaning that there was no significant role in the imbalance. The only state in which the second Chow test failed to reject the null hypothesis was California.

On the graph, e-commerce employment growth in California slows during the 2017-19 period. This could be due to the gradual exodus of businesses in California due to high operating costs in the state, which began around this period.

3.1 Trend analysis before and after the COVID-19 pandemic

To evaluate whether the COVID-19 pandemic permanently changed the rate of change of e-commerce employment growth, the t-test will be used to test whether the slopes of the two linear regression lines—one before the structural breakpoint (pre-pandemic data set) and the other after the structural breakpoint (post-pandemic data set) Since there are structural change breaks during Covid-19 from the previous structural analysis session, only before and after Covid-19 datasets are used for trend analysis.

- pre-pandemic (before March 1st, 2020)
- during pandemic (March 1st 2020 to February 1st, 2021)
- post-pandemic (After February 1st, 2021)

Such a split can be visualized in the graph below.

The below table shows that the t-statistic is less than the t-critical value for all states; there, the null hypothesis H_0 can not be rejected, which means that the slopes of before-pandemic and after-pandemic samples are not significantly different. The e-commerce employment trends are not significantly different between before the pandemic and after the pandemic.

Table 3: T-Statistic and Critical T-Value (Before and After the Pandemic)

OLS Results	California	Florida	Indiana	Wisconsin
$\beta_{2_{pre}}$	0.2350	0.0466	0.0459	-0.0360
$\beta_{2_{post}}$	-0.028	0.0759	-0.0815	-0.0959
$SE_{\hat{\beta}_2}$	0.004	0.001	0.002	0.001
$SE_{\hat{\beta}_{2_{post}}}$	0.019	0.033	0.009	0.006
df	148	39	36	27
t-statistic	1.1112	-0.3297	1.3620	0.5851
t-critical value	1.655	1.685	1.688	1.654
p-value	0.2683	0.7433	0.1817	0.5633
H_0 : slopes are not significant different	t < t-critical, failed to reject			

The results of the t-test showed that in each case (i.e., each of the four states), the t-critical value was higher than the t statistic, which meant that it failed to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the slopes are significantly different. This demonstrates that the rate of change for the e-commerce employee population has not changed from pre-pandemic levels in the post-pandemic environment. Aside from the initial shock and the sudden spike due to increased demand for online shopping, growth has been stable. For Indiana, the employment growth was slightly negative in the post-pandemic period.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Trends in California and Florida

E-commerce continues to be a leading creator of jobs in each of the four states. Since E-commerce companies rely heavily on the high-tech sector, it is no surprise that it continues to grow in states like California and Florida. In California, the Connected Commerce Council released a report in 2023 that studied digital sales and surveyed the

state's small businesses. It found that 60% of businesses have an online presence and that in 2022, 265 billion dollars in total came from online sales for small businesses.

The study also admits that for SMBs (small- medium businesses), online e-commerce is the best way to avoid political and societal turmoil (CCC, 2024). This is especially true for California. In the state's cities, businesses have been denouncing the rise in crime as a cause for changes and scalebacks in their business operations. Newsweek reported in 2024 that several businesses, including Target, Whole Foods, and Nordstrom, have closed stores in major California cities over targeted shoplifting, burglary, and concerns over customer safety (Carbonaro, 2024). Thus, businesses in California are adapting to supplying the large California market via online methods.

In Florida, the reopening took place much quicker than it did in California, albeit not without large surges in COVID cases over several months. Like in California, distribution centers and the tech industry continue to allow for job openings in the e-commerce industry. Florida's overall job growth has outpaced the nation in the year over March 2024, growing at a rate of 2.1% compared to the nationwide 1.7% (Florida Commerce, 2024). With infrastructure upgrades being discussed, Florida's e-commerce employee population still has room to grow. This can explain why both Florida and California have continued to see steady rises in the e-commerce employee population, similar to those of the pre-pandemic levels.

4.2 Trends in Indiana

In Indiana, the rate of change in e-commerce employment follows relatively closely with Florida and California. Indiana has had uneven economic development as a Rust Belt state. The Indianapolis and Fort Wayne metro areas have seen population growth—with the city proper increasing from a population of 805,423 in 2008 to 887,382 in 2020 (though the population declined slightly to 880,621 in 2022) (America Counts Staff, 2020). Amazon recently announced that it will be constructing a data center in Northern Indiana (CBS, 2024).

Florida and Indiana may have seen spikes in employment due to their different approaches to the pandemic. Indiana opened relatively quickly after the initial COVID-19 surge during the spring of 2020. In fact, the state gradually began reopening

from May 4, 2020, and reopened gyms and other recreational facilities by May 20, 2020 (Jaggers, 2021). This may explain the growth during the pandemic era and the post-pandemic era.

4.3 The Wisconsin Problem

Analyzing the time series, it becomes noticeable that even before the pandemic, Wisconsin's e-commerce employment numbers were decreasing rather than increasing. This trend only continued in the post-pandemic era. However, there seems to be conflicting data: total employment in the retail sector has remained stable from 2008 to 2022 in Wisconsin. In January 2008, the number of people working in the retail trade in Wisconsin was 309,400, while in December 2022, it was 356,000, not accounting for seasonal or unemployment adjustments. Interestingly enough, the number of employees in department stores also declined from 37,800 in January 2008 to less than 30,000 by the end of 2017, coinciding with the decline in employment in electronic shopping and mail-order houses (FRED, 2024).

Wisconsin has experienced economic challenges in certain regions and sectors. In October 2022, the labor participation rate declined to 65.5% from the 2019 level of over 66%. Even during the recovery period from the pandemic, this participation rate declined (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2024). This may be due to Wisconsin's aging population, which served as a roadblock to economic recovery from the pandemic (Wisconsin Department of Health, 2014).

Wisconsin also does not have a developed tech industry—something crucial for stable e-commerce industry job growth. While the state has tried to expand its high-tech sector, it lags behind other states (Cohn, 2024). The lack of a developed tech industry can stifle e-commerce start-ups. This is particularly evident when looking at the number of locally based e-commerce businesses in Wisconsin. Several include Sues Electronics, School Specialty, and Artful Homes. These businesses are much smaller than nationwide players, such as Amazon, which have a significant presence in larger metro areas.

A working-class population and large rural areas mean that Wisconsin's e-commerce industry faces challenges towards access and marketing, given that these demographics tend to favor more traditional retail. USDA reports that rural retail has

experienced growth from the rise of supercenters, along with dollar and convenience stores (Stevens, 2021). Morning Consult corroborates these claims (Tassin). If true, this can indicate why Wisconsin may have a steady retail industry despite the decline in traditional malls and e-commerce employment: the rise in other forms of physical retail. This can be supported by the fact that employment in general merchandise stores (including Walmart, 7-11, and other convenience stores) has surged since the pandemic after declining in the pre-pandemic era: rising from roughly 53,900 employees in February 2020 to 56,976 in December 2022 (FRED, 2024).

4.4 Traditional Retail

As all states gradually reopened, customers gradually reverted to in-person shopping. Instead of dying, brick-and-mortar retail is “evolving” and cites several key advantages that in-store shopping has over e-commerce. 5 in 10 surveyed customers prefer in-store shopping to survey the quality of products, and 80% of them preferred in-store shopping when prices for products are higher (Pryor, 2023).

Diaz Caldewey et al. stated that new housing development may generate higher demand for physical retail stores. They also argue that the recovery will depend on how changing attitudes towards traditional retail will continue to persist and the manner in which department store chains will respond to a decrease in foot traffic. The consensus is that a post-pandemic recovery is an opportunity for the survival of in-store businesses, but e-commerce's prevalence remains a challenge.

5. CONCLUSION

The structural break point in the time series of employee populations in all four states coincided with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. The population of employees increased permanently after the pandemic. However, the rate of change of e-commerce employment growth remains unchanged in the post-pandemic world compared to the pre-pandemic environment.

In California, the slope of the linear regression of the e-commerce employment population from January 2008 to February 2020 was 0.2350, and the slope of the linear regression from March 2021 to December 2022 was -0.028. There was no significant change in

the rate of change of the e-commerce employee population, and it also illustrates, therefore, that there is not a sustained trend of rapid growth similar to that which occurred during the structural break point during the initial lockdown period. Such findings were common in all four states: e-commerce employment growth either mirrored pre-pandemic growth rates or dropped slightly in the post-pandemic world.

This is in line with the conclusions from other papers. A study examining whether or not COVID-19 permanently changed e-commerce by analyzing e-commerce and retail sales posed a similar result: Although the onset of COVID-19 correlated with a rise in e-commerce sales, e-commerce sales have seen the rate of change stabilize or slightly decrease back to normal. The paper attributes this to the reopening of physical retail stores, driving customers back to in-person shopping (Genc, 2024).

Despite the growing online industry, there are still attributes of in-person shopping that customers seem unwilling to give up to substitute with online shopping. This includes being more enticed to buy from physical displays, interactive customer service, and chains beginning to use their foot traffic as a direct feed into their online services.

6. LIMITATIONS

Several limitations existed. Given that e-commerce employment has not been studied to the extent of sales, finding sources for a literature review proved a challenge. Secondly, the FRED did not include data for the four states during 2023 or 2024, making it more difficult to assess the post-pandemic behavior of e-commerce employment numbers.

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